

ENUMERATING PARTS OF n -COLOR PARTITIONS**Shruti Sharma**

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Abstract

In recent years, a number of authors have obtained numerous relations between the number of parts in restricted as well as unrestricted partitions and various functions from multiplicative number theory such as $\phi(m)$, $\tau(m)$, $\sigma(m)$, etc. In this paper, we seek similar kinds of relations for the number of parts in various restricted and unrestricted n -color partitions. Here, in particular, these relations occur with divisor functions.

1. Introduction

A *partition* of a positive integer m is a sequence of positive integers whose sum is m . While the order of positive integers in a partition does not matter, we conventionally list them in non-increasing order for consistency. These positive integers are also called the summands or parts of a partition. Many important partition identities involve restrictions on the parts of a partition. A very old and famous identity due to Euler equates the number of partitions into odd parts to the number of partitions into distinct parts. Partition identities also arise from counting the number of parts in a partition. In the literature, the first such identity is credited to Stanley, and its generalization to Elder. To know more about the history of these identities, the reader is referred to [5].

Theorem 1 (Stanley's theorem). *The number of 1's in the partitions of n equals the number of parts that appear at least once in a given partition of n , summed over all partitions of n .*

Theorem 2 (Elder’s theorem). *The number of appearances of a part k in the partitions of n is equal to the number of parts that appear at least k times in a given partition of n , summed over all partitions of n .*

Andrews and Merca’s work [3] provides a further generalization of Elder’s theorem. In [4], the authors count the number of even parts in partitions into distinct parts. Merca [6] investigated specific restricted partitions, enumerating their parts and establishing relationships between these counts and the divisors of m . In [7, 8], the authors obtained numerous relations between the number of parts in partitions (restricted as well as unrestricted) and various functions from multiplicative number theory such as $\phi(m)$, $\tau(m)$, $\sigma(m)$, etc. In order to obtain these relations, they used the Lambert series, which is given by

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{a_m q^m}{1 - q^m}, \quad |q| < 1,$$

where the a_m for $m = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ are real or complex numbers. This series is a natural generalization of the formula

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{a_m q^m}{1 - q^m} = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} b_{\pm}(m) q^m,$$

where

$$b_{\pm}(m) = \sum_{d|m} (\mp 1)^{1+m/d} a_d.$$

When working with n -color partitions, it is natural for us to seek similar kinds of relations for the number of parts in various restricted and unrestricted n -color partitions. In this manuscript, however, we will focus only on the divisor functions. For a reader who is not exposed to the theory of n -color partitions, we include the definition of n -color partitions as given in [2]. An n -color partition of a positive integer is a partition, in which a part of size m can occur in m different colors denoted by subscripts m_1, m_2, \dots, m_m . For example, the n -color partitions of 3 are

$$3_1, 3_2, 3_3, 2_2 + 1_1, 2_1 + 1_1, 1_1 + 1_1 + 1_1.$$

Let $P(m)$ denote the number of partitions of m . Then,

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} P(m) q^m = \frac{1}{\prod_{m=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^m)}.$$

As a convention, we take $P(0)$ as 1. Using similar notation, we write

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} C(m) q^m = \frac{1}{\prod_{m=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^m)^m}, \tag{1}$$

where $C(m)$ is the number of n -color partitions of m and $C(0) = 1$.

As ordinary partitions have been studied with various restrictions, n -color partitions too can be considered with restrictions on the parts and colors. Generating functions for the number of n -color partitions with various restrictions were provided by Agarwal [1]. However, we take into account some of these n -color partitions with restrictions while studying the number of parts. We include the generating functions for $C(D, m)$, $C(O, m)$, and $C(E, m)$, which denote, respectively, the number of n -color partitions into distinct parts, into odd parts, and into even parts of a positive integer m . Also, we take $C(D, 0) = C(O, 0) = C(E, 0) = 1$ as a convention. The generating functions for $C(D, m)$, $C(O, m)$, and $C(E, m)$ are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} C(D, m)q^m &= \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} (1 + q^m)^m, \\ \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} C(O, m)q^m &= \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1 - q^{2m-1})^{2m-1}}, \\ \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} C(E, m)q^m &= \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1 - q^{2m})^{2m}}. \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Let $C_{e-o}(m)$ denote the number of n -color partitions of a positive integer m into an even number of parts minus the number of n -color partitions of a positive integer m into an odd number of parts. We can easily obtain the following generating function for $C_{e-o}(m)$, where we take $C_{e-o}(0) = 1$:

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} C_{e-o}(m)q^m = \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1 + q^m)^m}. \tag{3}$$

Now, we let $C_{od}(m)$ denote the number of n -color partitions of m wherein odd parts are distinct and even parts are unrestricted and $C_{ed}(m)$ denote the number of n -color partitions of m wherein even parts are distinct and odd parts are unrestricted. Again, we take $C_{od}(0) = 1$ and $C_{ed}(0) = 1$ to obtain the following generating functions for $C_{od}(m)$ and $C_{ed}(m)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} C_{od}(m)q^m &= \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1 + q^{2m-1})^{2m-1}}{(1 - q^{2m})^{2m}}, \\ \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} C_{ed}(m)q^m &= \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1 + q^{2m})^{2m}}{(1 - q^{2m-1})^{2m-1}}. \end{aligned}$$

In Section 2, we enumerate the parts of n -color partitions without restrictions and investigate their relationship with various divisor functions. In Section 3, we investigate similar relations while counting the number of parts of n -color partitions with restrictions.

2. Number of Parts in n -Color Partitions and Divisor Functions

We start this section by summing the number of parts for all the n -color partitions into an odd (even) number of parts which provides us our first result.

Theorem 3. *Let $T_o(m)$ (respectively $T_e(m)$) denote the sum of the number of parts, where the sum is taken over all the n -color partitions of a positive integer m into an odd (respectively even) number of parts. Then for $|q| < 1$,*

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{mq^m}{1 \mp q^m} = \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} (1 \mp q^m)^m \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (T_o(m) \pm T_e(m))q^m.$$

Proof. Considering the generating function for n -color partitions and introducing a new variable x which keeps track of the number of parts, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (T_o(m) \pm T_e(m))q^m &= \left. \frac{d}{dx} \right|_{x=\pm 1} \{(1-xq)^{-1}(1-xq^2)^{-2} \dots\} \\ &= \frac{1}{\prod_{m=1}^{\infty} (1 \mp q^m)^m} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{mq^m}{1 \mp q^m}. \end{aligned}$$

This concludes our proof. □

We also have the following results from sequences A000593, A146076, and A000203 in the OEIS [9]:

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{mq^m}{1+q^m} = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2m-1)q^{2m-1}}{1-q^{2m-1}} = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sigma_{odd}(m)q^m, \tag{4}$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{2mq^{2m}}{1-q^{2m}} = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sigma_{even}(m)q^m, \tag{5}$$

where $\sigma_{even}(m)$ (respectively, $\sigma_{odd}(m)$) is the sum of even divisors (respectively, odd divisors) of m .

Also,

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2m-1)q^{2m-1}}{1+q^{2m-1}} = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{m+1} \sigma_{odd}(m)q^m$$

and

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{mq^m}{1-q^m} = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sigma(m)q^m, \quad |q| < 1, \tag{6}$$

where $\sigma(m)$ denotes the sum of divisors of m . Now, using Equations (1), (2), (4), and (6), we get Corollary 1 and Corollary 2 to Theorem 3 with the help of convolution properties.

Corollary 1. *For any positive integer m ,*

$$T_o(m) + T_e(m) = \sum_{k=1}^m \sigma(k)C(m - k). \tag{7}$$

We take an example to verify Corollary 1 for $m = 4$.

Example 1. n -color partitions of 4 into an odd number of parts are

$$4_1, 4_2, 4_3, 4_4, 2_2 + 1_1 + 1_1, 2_1 + 1_1 + 1_1,$$

and into an even number of parts are

$$3_1 + 1_1, 3_2 + 1_1, 3_3 + 1_1, 2_2 + 2_2, 2_2 + 2_1, 2 + 1 + 1_1, 1_1 + 1_1 + 1_1 + 1_1.$$

Thus, $T_o(4) = 10$ and $T_e(4) = 16$. We know $\sigma(1) = 1, \sigma(2) = 3, \sigma(3) = 4,$ and $\sigma(4) = 7$. Also, $C(3) = 6, C(2) = 3, C(1) = 1,$ and $C(0) = 1$. On substituting all these values and $m = 4$ in (7), we see that

$$T_o(4) + T_e(4) = \sum_{k=1}^4 \sigma(k)C(4 - k).$$

Corollary 2. *For any positive integer m ,*

$$\sigma_{odd}(m) = \sum_{k=1}^m (T_o(k) - T_e(k)) C(D, m - k).$$

In Theorem 4, we count the number of even parts in all the n -color partitions.

Theorem 4. *Let $A_e(m)$ denote the sum of the number of even parts, where the sum is taken over all the n -color partitions of a positive integer m . Then for $|q| < 1,$*

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{2mq^{2m}}{1 - q^{2m}} = \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^m)^m \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} A_e(m)q^m.$$

Proof. Proceeding in a similar manner as in the previous theorem, we see that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} A_e(m)q^m &= \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1 - q^{2m-1})^{2m-1}} \frac{d}{dx} \Big|_{x=1} \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1 - xq^{2m})^{2m}} \\ &= \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1 - q^m)^m} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{2mq^{2m}}{1 - q^{2m}}. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. □

As a direct consequence of Equations (1) and (5), we obtain the following corollary of Theorem 4.

Corollary 3. *For any positive integer m ,*

$$A_e(m) = \sum_{k=1}^m \sigma_{\text{even}}(k)C(m - k).$$

Theorem 5 is similar to Theorem 4 with the only difference being that we now count the number of odd parts.

Theorem 5. *Let $A_o(m)$ represent the sum of the number of odd parts, where the sum is taken over all the n -color partitions of a positive integer m . Then for $|q| < 1$,*

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2m - 1)q^{2m-1}}{1 - q^{2m-1}} = \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^m)^m \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} A_o(m)q^m.$$

Corollary 4. *For any positive integer m ,*

$$A_o(m) = \sum_{k=1}^m \sigma_{\text{odd}}(k)C(m - k).$$

Our next result is about counting the number of parts with multiple occurrences.

Theorem 6. *For positive integers m and t , let $N^t(m)$ denote the sum of the number of distinct parts with multiplicity at least t , where the sum is taken over all the n -color partitions of m . Then,*

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} mq^{mt} = \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^m)^m \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} N^t(m)q^m, \quad m \geq t.$$

Proof. We can obtain the generating function for $N^t(m)$ by introducing a variable x to account for the number of parts with multiplicity at least t , then taking derivative with respect to x and finally substituting $x = 1$. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} N^t(m)q^m &= \left. \frac{d}{dx} \right|_{x=1} \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} \left(1 + q^m + \dots + q^{(t-1)m} + x \frac{q^{mt}}{1 - q^m} \right)^m \\ &= \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1 - q^m)^m} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} mq^{mt}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Corollary 5. *For positive integers m and t ,*

$$N^t(m) = \sum_{k=1}^{\lfloor m/t \rfloor} kC(m - tk), \quad m \geq t.$$

In Theorem 7, we count number of parts congruent to $k \pmod r$ for some fixed positive integers k and r .

Theorem 7. For $r \geq 1$ and $0 < k < r$, let $C(k_{\text{mod } r}, m)$ denote the sum of the number of parts congruent to $k \pmod r$, where the sum is taken over all the n -color partitions of a positive integer m . Then,

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(rm+k)q^{rm+k}}{1-q^{rm+k}} = \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} (1-q^m)^m \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} C(k_{\text{mod } r}, m)q^m.$$

Proof. In the following two variable generating function, x keeps track of parts congruent to $k \pmod r$ in all the n -color partitions:

$$\prod_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \not\equiv k \pmod r}}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-q^i)^i} \prod_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \equiv k \pmod r}}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-xq^j)^j}.$$

By applying $\frac{d}{dx} \Big|_{x=1}$ to the above expression, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} C(k_{\text{mod } r}, m)q^m &= \prod_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \not\equiv k \pmod r}}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-q^i)^i} \prod_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \equiv k \pmod r}}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-q^i)^i} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(rm+k)q^{rm+k}}{1-q^{rm+k}} \\ &= \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-q^m)^m} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(rm+k)q^{rm+k}}{1-q^{rm+k}}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Corollary 6. For integers $m > 0$, $r \geq 1$ and $0 < k < r$,

$$C(k_{\text{mod } r}, m) = \sum_{j=1}^m \left(\sum_{rd+k|j} (rd+k) \right) C(m-j).$$

3. Number of Parts in n -Color Partitions with Restrictions and Divisor Functions

In this section, we focus on counting the number of parts in some restricted n -color partitions and we start by considering n -color partitions into distinct parts.

Theorem 8. Let $C_o(D, m)$ (respectively $C_e(D, m)$) denote the sum of the number of parts, where the sum is taken over all the n -color partitions of a positive integer m into an odd (respectively even) number of distinct parts. Then for $|q| < 1$,

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{mq^m}{1 \pm q^m} = \frac{1}{\prod_{m=1}^{\infty} (1 \pm q^m)^m} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (C_o(D, m) \pm C_e(D, m)) q^m.$$

Proof. Proceeding in a manner similar to the proof of Theorem 3, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (C_o(D, m) \pm C_e(D, m)) q^m &= \frac{d}{dx} \Big|_{x=\pm 1} \{ (1+xq)(1+xq^2)^2(1+xq^3)^3 \dots \} \\ &= \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} (1+xq^m)^m \left\{ \frac{q}{1+xq} + \frac{2q^2}{1+xq^2} + \dots \right\} \Big|_{x=\pm 1} \\ &= \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} (1 \pm q^m)^m \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{mq^m}{1 \pm q^m}, \end{aligned}$$

which gives us the desired result. □

To obtain Corollaries 7-9 to Theorem 8, we use Equations (1), (2), (3), (4), (6), and the Cauchy product of two power series.

Corollary 7. *For any positive integer m,*

$$C_o(D, m) + C_e(D, m) = \sum_{k=1}^m \sigma_{\text{odd}}(k) C(D, m - k).$$

Corollary 8. *For any positive integer m,*

$$\sigma(m) = \sum_{k=1}^m (C_o(D, k) - C_e(D, k)) C(m - k).$$

Corollary 9. *For any positive integer m,*

$$\sigma_{\text{odd}}(m) = \sum_{k=1}^m C(D, k) C_{e-o}(m - k).$$

Proceeding in a similar manner as in Theorem 8, we can prove Theorem 9.

Theorem 9. *Let Q(O, m) represent sum of the number of parts, where the sum is taken over all the n-color partitions of a positive integer m into odd parts. Then for |q| < 1,*

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2m-1)q^{2m-1}}{1-q^{2m-1}} = \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} (1-q^{2m-1})^{2m-1} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} Q(O, m)q^m.$$

Corollary 10. *For any positive integer m,*

$$Q(O, m) = \sum_{k=1}^m \sigma_{\text{odd}}(k) C(O, m - k).$$

Similar results can be proved for the number of parts in all the n -color partitions of a positive integer into even parts.

Our next theorem is related to the set of n -color partitions with distinct odd parts and unrestricted even parts.

Theorem 10. *Let $Q_{od}(m)$ represent the sum of the number of parts, where the sum is taken over all the n -color partitions of a positive integer m with distinct odd parts and unrestricted even parts. Then for $|q| < 1$,*

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2m-1)q^{2m-1}}{1+q^{2m-1}} = \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1-q^{2m})^{2m}}{(1+q^{2m-1})^{2m-1}} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} Q_{od}(m)q^m.$$

Corollary 11. *For a positive integer m ,*

$$Q_{od}(m) = \sum_{k=1}^m \left[\sum_{2d-1|k} (-1)^{1+k/2d-1} (2d-1) \right] C_{od}(m-k).$$

Again, similar results can be proved for $Q_{ed}(m)$, where $Q_{ed}(m)$ represents the sum of the number of parts with the sum taken over all the n -color partitions of a non-negative integer into distinct even parts and unrestricted odd parts.

Theorem 11 is also about counting the number of parts in n -color partitions into distinct parts but here we count some fixed part.

Theorem 11. *For $j \geq 1$, let $Q(D, j, m)$ denote the sum of the number of j 's, where the sum is taken over all the n -color partitions of a positive integer m into distinct parts. Then for $|q| < 1$,*

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} Q(D, j, m)q^m = \frac{jq^j}{1+q^j} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} C(D, m)q^m.$$

Proof. To prove this result, we introduce a variable x to count the total number of j 's in all the n -color partitions of m into distinct parts. Then, we take the derivative with respect to x and put $x = 1$. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} Q(D, j, m)q^m &= \left. \frac{d}{dx} \right|_{x=1} (1+xq^j)^j \prod_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq j}}^{\infty} (1+q^i)^i \\ &= \frac{jq^j}{1+q^j} \prod_{i \geq 1} (1+q^i)^i \\ &= \frac{jq^j}{1+q^j} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} C(D, m)q^m. \end{aligned}$$

□

In Theorem 12, we restrict the n -color partitions to those having an odd (respectively even) number of parts, with the added restriction that all parts are odd.

Theorem 12. *Let $U_e(m)$ (respectively $U_o(m)$) denote the sum of the number of parts, where the sum is taken over all the odd n -color partitions of a positive integer m into an odd (respectively even) number of parts. Then for $|q| < 1$,*

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2m-1)q^{2m-1}}{(1 \mp q^{2m-1})^{2m-1}} = \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} (1 \mp q^{2m-1})^{2m-1} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (U_o(m) \pm U_e(m)) q^m.$$

Corollary 12. *For any positive integer m ,*

$$U_o(m) + U_e(m) = \sum_{k=1}^m \sigma_{\text{odd}}(k) C(O, m-k).$$

Corollary 13. *Let $C(O, D, m)$ denote the number of n -color partitions of a positive integer m into distinct odd parts. Then,*

$$(-1)^{m+1} \sigma_{\text{odd}}(m) = \sum_{k=1}^m (U_o(k) - U_e(k)) C(O, D, m-k).$$

The generating function for $C(O, D, m)$ is given by

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} C(O, D, m) q^m = \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} (1 + q^{2m-1})^{2m-1}.$$

4. Conclusion

The findings reported in this paper are based solely on analytic methods. It is always desirable to establish combinatorial proofs as these give better insight. However, the biggest constraint in achieving this goal is the absence of Ferrers diagram-like representation for n -color partitions. In fact, if someone is able to think of any such representation for n -color partitions, it will open a world of possibilities in the theory of n -color partitions.

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